

CREATING MORE FACILITIES FOR GUIDES IN PROMOTING TOURISM

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Abstract. Until recently, the work of a guide was not considered a profession, it was only an interesting activity for a group of amateurs. The work of the guide was carried out by specialists of various fields without separating from their main activities (pedagogues, scientific staff of the museum, scientific staff of the institute, etc.). Only a few excursion institutions and individual museums in the state had guides. But over time, this activity began to acquire professional characteristics.

Keywords: guide, tourism, profession, activity, method, opportunity.

INTRODUCTION

The change in the function of the excursion service, its transformation from a form of recreation to an organizational form of cultural and educational work in labor communities and a service network for the population, led to the rise of a new specialty, that is, the role of a guide.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism" includes the concepts of tourist group leader (tour leader) and tour guide (excursion leader). According to it, "the leader of the tourist group is a natural person who is a representative of the subjects of tourist activity and acts on his behalf and ensures the fulfillment of the terms of the service contract for tourists", "Guide (excursion leader) - provides tourist services to the participants of the tour within the scope of the performance contract, the definitions "excursion-information, organizational services and qualified assistance" are included.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formation of the profession of a guide is complex and multifaceted. It can be divided into the following 4 stages

Table 1

Stages of formation of the profession of guide

Stages	Process name	Place of action
1	The formation of the desire to conduct cultural collective work with people	In public schools, club institutions
2	Having a system of knowledge in a specialty	Vocational education, courses, independent study
3	Learning the basics of professional skills	Guide preparatory courses, tourism specialty at the Higher Education Institution
4	Improvement of knowledge, qualifications, skills in the specialty	Advanced training courses in guiding methodical circles

Professional requirements. To people who choose the profession of a guide, this profession imposes several requirements, namely, the desire to participate in cultural and educational activities, the essence of the excursion service in the educational process, the understanding of one's role in it, a sense of duty, one or more topics of the excursion having accurate

knowledge, not being indifferent to uncultured and old-fashioned views, continuously improving their knowledge, striving for innovation, showing initiative and creative approach to work, interesting and studying the demands of tourists, different approach to serving people of different groups; education, high culture and behavior, should have the right relationship with excursionists, have the style of providing excursion services, in short, should know the secrets of the profession well.

The profession of a guide requires specific practical skills. This qualification gives him the opportunity to correctly select, embody and effectively transfer his knowledge to the audience. Those who have chosen the profession of a guide should be able to: choose the necessary, specific information, read and study, prepare an individual text for an excursion on a specific topic, create a methodical guide, apply them in practice, create a "guide portfolio" correct and timely use of visual aids, exchange experience with other guides, participate in promotion of excursion opportunities of the region, etc [4].

Specialization is one of the main areas of improvement of the professional skills of the guide. First of all, we will determine the meaning and relationship between two concepts such as "profession" and "specialty". Profession is a form of labor activity that requires specific knowledge and skills. A specialty is a type of activity within a profession. For example: a doctor is a profession, a therapist, a surgeon, a dentist is a specialty, etc. If the profession is the main type of activity, the concept of "specialization" indicates the level of knowledge and skill achievement within a certain profession, i.e. a specialist is a worker who has a professional mastery of a specialty.

The main qualities of a person can include the following [5]:

- prudence - act with intelligence;
- responsibility - understanding the result of one's actions;
- personal reputation - actions related to the protection of one's rights;
- individuality - uniqueness of personality, non-repetition.

The knowledge, skills, and abilities that positively characterize a guide are primarily based on his ability to perform the work assigned to him. In the process of training guides, stylists take into account that they have the necessary skills to be able to prepare a new excursion topic, write abstracts, give lectures on courses, conduct excursions on routes, and choose a methodological guide.

CONCLUSION

Regardless of how well the guide has mastered the subject, he is prepared every time. The success of the preparatory stage depends on the individual characteristics of the guide's personality, that is, the speed and organizational ability to perform the necessary work. The concept of "preparation" also includes mental preparation. In this case, he believes in his own knowledge, that is, he is confident that he will provide the excursion service at a high level, that the excursionists will be satisfied and happy with what they see and hear.

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